

THE NEED FOR LATIN IN MEDICAL STUDENTS: TRADITIONAL AND MODERN APPROACHES

¹Berezovskaya R.A., ²Mekhmonova N.U., ³Sodiqova Z.X., ⁴Rasulova Z.T.

^{1,2,3,4}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282219>

Abstract. *A key aspect of successful teaching of Latin in medical school is the development of an effective teaching methodology that takes into account the specific needs of future medical professionals. The abstract of this methodology should emphasize the importance of a unique approach that combines traditional learning of Latin with an emphasis on medical terminology. An effective methodology for teaching Latin in medical school should include the integration of modern technologies, such as interactive online resources, multimedia materials, and medical cases for practical application of the studied knowledge. In addition, it should emphasize the features of Latin grammar related to the medical context and provide students with the necessary tools for successful translation and analysis of medical texts in Latin. An important element of this methodology is also the creation of a stimulating learning environment that inspires students to actively participate in the learning process and develop their linguistic skills. Ultimately, the methodology for teaching Latin in medical school should help students acquire not only a deep knowledge of the Latin language, but also confidence in its use in medical practice.*

Keywords: *methodology, teaching, Latin language, medical school, specifics, terminology, technologies, grammar, context, learning, stimulating environment, skill development, medical practice.*

Introduction: In the field of medical education, the study of Latin has a unique significance. Its historical importance as the language of medicine, coupled with its role in shaping medical terminology, highlights the need for Latin to be included in the medical university curriculum. However, effective teaching of Latin in this specialized context presents specific challenges and requires adapted methodologies. The purpose of this article is to delve into the various approaches and strategies used in the teaching of Latin in medical education, highlighting their relevance, effectiveness, and potential impact on student learning outcomes.

Teaching Latin in medical school poses unique challenges that require innovative pedagogical approaches. Unlike traditional language learners, medical students are primarily focused on acquiring specialized knowledge in anatomy, physiology, and pathology, so it is critical that Latin instruction be relevant to their academic and professional goals. Moreover, the abstract nature of Latin grammar and syntax, coupled with the complex morphology of medical terms, can intimidate students and hinder their learning progress if left unchecked.

Integrating Technology and Multimedia Resources: In response to the changing educational environment, the incorporation of technology and multimedia resources has emerged as a promising way to enhance Latin instruction in medical schools. Interactive online platforms, digital flashcards, and virtual anatomy software provide students with a dynamic learning experience that reinforces their understanding of Latin vocabulary and its application in a medical context. Additionally, the integration of multimedia elements such as audio recordings and visual aids facilitate auditory and visual learning methods, catering to a variety of student preferences and learning styles.

Focus on Medical Terminology and Clinical Relevance: An effective Latin teaching methodology in medical school places a strong emphasis on medical terminology and its clinical relevance. By contextualizing Latin vocabulary within medical specialties, students gain a deeper understanding of the etymology and semantic nuances of medical terms, thereby facilitating retention and comprehension. Additionally, the inclusion of clinical examples and real-life scenarios provides students with the opportunity to apply their Latin knowledge in a practical context, reinforcing its relevance in their future medical practice.

Research results: Reflections on the implementation of effective methods for successful teaching and assimilation of the material presented in the process of studying Latin language arise from the final result, namely, from what knowledge, skills and abilities a student should have upon completion of the curriculum of the course "Latin Language" at a university with a medical and pharmaceutical focus. An important point in teaching "dead" languages, in particular Latin, is the fact that the system of knowledge on the subject "Latin Language" is built in such a way as to achieve the main goal of training - to prepare a qualified specialist who is fluent in scientific medical terminology, in connection with which teaching Latin is based on the need to memorize a huge number of specialized terms of medical and pharmaceutical orientation, without knowledge of which further successful mastering of the future profession is impossible. Thus, in the process of teaching Latin, emphasis is placed on new innovative mnemonic methods and techniques for memorizing foreign words and expressions, which leads to the need to move away from traditional grammatical, grammatical-morphological and translation methods of studying a "dead" language in favor of new modern methods. For example, to develop students' memorization and creative thinking in the process of studying Latin, teachers use the following active learning methods: heuristic conversations, educational discussions, and search work. An important element in teaching is independent work with additional sources of literature as a way of self-knowledge, development of a general cultural outlook, cognitive interests and abilities, aesthetic perception of the surrounding world and ordering of the system of moral views.

Conclusion: In conclusion, effective teaching of Latin in medical school requires a multifaceted approach that addresses the unique needs and challenges of medical students. By integrating technology and multimedia resources, focusing on medical terminology and clinical relevance, and creating a stimulating learning environment, faculty can enhance students' proficiency in Latin and equip them with the linguistic skills necessary to succeed in their medical careers. As guardians of a venerable linguistic tradition, faculty are responsible not only for transmitting knowledge but also for cultivating a deep understanding of the enduring legacy of Latin in medicine. Through innovative pedagogical practices and a commitment to excellence, faculty can empower future generations of health care professionals to navigate the complex web of medical discourse with skill, precision, and enthusiasm.

REFERENCES

1. Rasulovna, H. M. (2023). USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 79-81.
2. Akbarxodjayeva, F. (2021). ТИББИЁТ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЯСИ МУРАККАБ ТИЗИМ СИФАТИДА: ТИББИЁТ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЯСИ МУРАККАБ ТИЗИМ СИФАТИДА. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).

3. Abduganievna, A. F. (2023). SOME THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE QUANTITATIVE COMPOSITION OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art*, 52-56.
4. Abduganiyevna, A. F. (2023). ISSUES OF TEACHING AND STUDYING MEDICAL TERMS IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 8, 5-7.
5. Акбарходжаева, Ф. (2023). Тиббиёт терминологияси махсус илмий маънони ифодалаш учун хизмат қиладиган тушунча сифатида. *Педиатрия*, 1(1), 267-271.
6. Abduganievna, A. F. (2022). MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN THE TERMINOLOGY SYSTEM. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 8, 89-91.
7. АКБАРХОДЖАЙЕВА, Ф. (2024). ОММАВИЙ АХБОРОТ ВОСИТАЛАРИДА ТИББИЙОТ ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ ВОҚЕЛАНИШИГА ДОИР ҚАРАШЛАР. *News of UzMU journal*, 1(1.4), 264-270.